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LEARNERS' AND TEACHERS' EXPERIENCES ON THE USE OF GENYO eLEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM: BASES FOR ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

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Abstract

This research paper aimed to find out the learners' and teachers' experiences on the use of Genyo eLearning Management System (LMS) as bases for enhancement program using the phenomenological approach under descriptive-qualitative method. The participants of the study were eight (8) Junior High School learners and eight (8) Junior High School teachers who utilize Genyo eLearning Management in Colegio de San Jose, Jaro, Iloilo City, Inc. The data were gathered using a researcher-made questionnaire through in-depth interviews. The results stressed about the learners' background in Genyo eLearning Management System, how they access the Genyo, their hindrances and facilitating factors and the implementation of the Genyo as a tool. On the other hand, teachers also expressed their views, experiences, hindering and facilitating factors and shared the steps on how to administer the LMS. To help the learners and teachers successfully adopt the Genyo eLearning Management System an enhancement program entitled Genyo eLearning Enhancement Program was proposed. Suggestions were given to help learners and teachers enhance their skills in using the Genyo eLearning Management System.

Keywords: Learners' and Teachers' Experiences, Use of Genyo eLearning Management System, Enhancement Program

1. Introduction:

It is evidently noticeable that technology play a vital role in our daily lives. Learning Management System is a tool that provides a meaningful learning for asynchronous and synchronous classes. This tool has different features that are important in uploading learning materials such as lesson packages, quizzes, games and interactive activities.

Educational institutions like Colegio de San Jose, Jaro, Iloilo City, Inc. have adopted Genyo eLearning Management System to provide the needs of the learners for an interactive and meaningful learning experience. It is designed to be used by both learners and teachers, especially in pandemic scenarios.

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Additionally, teachers use the Genyo eLearning site to access additional learning resources where they can publish tests and supplemental activities to improve student learning.

The uploaded activities are being access by learners during distance learning to suffice their needs during the pandemic years.

Learners and teachers are not familiar with Genyo eLearning Management System as a new learning tool therefore, using its features are not maximized. In order to properly use the Learning Management System (LMS) and improve classroom interactions, a series of trainings were provided so that teachers are guided in using the different features offered. This hands-on trainings also consider the possible difficulties that could occur with this new learning tool. Moreover, to ensure that they are competent in using the platform for information access and assignment submission, students should also be given technical support (Alenezi, 2018).

The researcher aims to find out the views and experiences of the learners and teachers on the use of Genyo eLearning Management System to provide meaningful teaching and learning process with the use of Genyo eLearning Management System.

2. Methodology

The study used a descriptive-qualitative research design using in-depth interviews to gather experiences of learners and teachers in using the Genyo eLearning Management System.

Phenomenological Approach was used to describe and record the experiences of the participants and to create a thorough description of the core of the specific phenomena (Neubauer et al., 2019). The goal of the structured interview was to gain the participants' thoughts and insights by having them react to a series of questions about their views and experiences using the Genyo eLearning Management System as a group. The talk was facilitated by the researcher using an interview guide made specifically for this study. Thematic analysis was used to examine qualitative data, including coded and processed recorded interviews and transcripts. Following the instructions provided in the thematic analysis technique, the process comprised identifying themes and sub-themes.

The participants of the study were eight (8) Junior High School learners and eight (8) Junior High School teachers of Colegio de San Jose, Jaro, Iloilo City, Inc. for the school year 2022-2023.

3. Results

According to the findings of the study, it became clearer that learners see the Genyo eLearning Management System as a helpful educational platform, especially during distance learning sessions to maintain the continuity of learning. They claimed to finish teacher-provided assignments even while relaxing in their own houses.

Although, initially learners and teachers were unfamiliar with the platform, a series of orientations were provided to them so that they will progressively picked up how to use the LMS's capabilities. The tools and methods used to manage the entire process are evolving as well as the pedagogical approaches used in the classroom as online learning continues. Given this circumstance, it is advised that students to be prepared

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for probable internet failures or power outages since these are frequent problems when using the LMS.

Also, Genyo eLearning Management System is technically a user-friendly platform for teachers to create and upload learning materials online. Thus, teachers creatively personalized their lesson packages because of easy and manageable features offered by Genyo. It also caters the needs of the learners in terms of giving comments and suggestions to give feedback from the activities posted in the LMS. Through the intervention of teachers, there was an increase of learners' engagement and improves learning outcome.

Furthermore, with the involvement of IT experts, teachers are motivated in exploring features to provide the needs of the learners in adopting to LMS and make life easier regardless of their level of expertise or newness to the field. This is because it helps them stay organized, flexible, and open when interacting with learners, parents, and administrators.

4. Discussions

Learning Management System is an educational tool that provide learners and teachers to access for the continuity of learning especially to fill the gap of distance learning. With the intervention of technology, using an LMS becomes a need to be competitive to the different trends of learning so that it could offer the learners a meaningful learning experience. In times of online learning has expanded quickly, not only the teaching techniques used in traditional classrooms changed, but also the tools and procedures used to manage the entire process of teaching-learning (Brown et al., 2014).

Genyo eLearning Management System is a learning tool adopted in Colegio de San Jose, Jaro, Iloilo City, Inc. It allows teachers to upload supplemental activities for learning. Furthermore, learners also access through their log in details to answer the activities and download lesson packages. Thus, Genyo is utilized as learning material due to online learning to complete activities and achieve the intended learning results (Bradley, 2021).

Learners' engagement to LMS improves communication, collaboration, and accessibility to educational resources. The study is anchored to the Theory of connectivism, in which it is an innovative learning theory, which proposes that, in order to learn effectively, students should embrace the integration of thoughts, theories, and information that one experiences when using modern day technology (Kurt, 2023). Like any learning theory, connectivism has its share of supporters and critics. Spontaneous acquisition of knowledge and reflective thinking are produced through a special internal mechanism known as mindfulness (Kropf, 2013). Learners are enjoying in the activities posted by the teacher. Learners boost motivation because of the interactive activities in which Genyo eLearning has to offer. Learners were able to engage with this learning activities during asynchronous class because Genyo has all-inone package where teachers upload learning materials and make learners feel easy and convenient while learning. Trainings are also provided to improve learners' and teachers' skills in technicalities in managing the LMS.

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According to Rogers' Theory of Diffusion of Innovations, (Ouyang and Stanley, 2015) the theory is widely applied in educational technology training. Its application value is that the training department and trainers are able to match the training plan and design with trainees' beliefs, attitudes and motivation to accept new trends of technology which teachers highly needed. With this, teachers will be equipped with relevant and modern approaches for the benefit of learners.

5. Conclusion

Based from the results of the study, the researcher concludes that it became a helpful learning platform for learners and teachers in facilitating learning. The tool was able to customize its time frame to consider factors that may arise while the learners are answering the activities. Through distance learning, the learners finish uploaded activities at home. Similarly, teachers find Genyo as convenient platform in giving activities. They are well guided by the technicians assigned to explore all of its features. It also saves time especially in generating the scores of the learners. Learners and teachers who has immense experience in technology found it easy and advantageous in exploring the platform and adapt immediately to the distance learning. In a blended learning setting, it was proposed to have integration of LMS such as Genyo eLearning enhancement program during face-to-face classes to utilize Genyo to have a collaborative and interactive mode of learning with the use of technology inside the classroom.

6. Recommendation

Before adopting the Genyo eLearning Management System, training should be required. With the support coming from the school administration, it aims to maximize utilization of the LMS. This suggestion will greatly improve the learning opportunities for students during class time and encourage them to frequently use the platform as a useful learning tool. Teachers will also be honored for their dedication and labor in creating educational materials that students may easily access through Genyo.

By using the Genyo eLearning Management System, school managers may streamline data gathering and lessen the amount of paperwork that teachers need to complete. It may be advantageous for subject area coordinators to use this method to collect information on teacher and student performance, making it simpler to pinpoint Learning Action Cell (LAC) subjects. A Genyo eLearning Management System customization for non-teaching employees may be investigated by the IT focal point.

Additionally, guidance counselors and parents should collaborate to help teachers and students use the Genyo eLearning Management System to address their mental and social requirements.

Future researchers should consider exploring the effect of Genyo eLearning on students and teachers' performance during pandemic in the local context.

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